

CHARACTERISING THE HOT DRAPE FORMING PROCESS AND THE EFFECT OF FIBRE SHEARING ON THE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF HIGHLY DRAPED COMPOSITE COMPONENTS

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SUMMARY: The hot drape forming process has been identified as a potential method of reducing manufacturing costs. This process consists of forming flat laminates into components incorporating complex curvature. Intra-ply shearing occurs during the forming process which has a detrimental effect on the mechanical properties of the final component. This paper outlines development trials conducted to identify the most significant parameters affecting the forming process. These were shown to be: vacuum rate, laminate geometry and forming temperature. The effect of intra-ply shearing is demonstrated through structural testing of hemispherical formed components. Two techniques are used to predict the effect of intra-ply shearing; Classical laminate theory and modified rule of mixtures. These methods are incorporated into a finite element analysis which is compared to the experimental data from the hemisphere tests. The modified rule of mixtures produced the most accurate results, however, further refinement of the finite element model is required.

KEYWORDS: hot drape forming, intra-ply shearing, mechanical properties, classical laminate theory, rule of mixtures, finite element analysis

INTRODUCTION

Composite materials consisting of continuous aligned fibre reinforcement are widely used for structural applications due to their high specific strength and stiffness. Manufacture of composite components within the aerospace industry is generally accomplished through low volume labour intensive manufacturing strategies based upon vacuum bagging and autoclaving. Hot drape forming of composite materials has been identified as a potential method of reducing the manufacturing costs of components with complex geometry. During the forming process, shearing of the fibres changes the directional properties of the material. This can have adverse effects on the structural properties of the final component.

Whilst a considerable degree of work has been performed in simulating the fibre deformation during forming, there has been little effort to characterise the forming process and the effect of fibre shear experimentally. The purpose of this paper is to establish the variables that have the greatest effect on the hot drape forming process. Experiments are performed using a hemispherical tool to investigate the effect of vacuum rate, test piece geometry and forming temperature. Two alternative models are proposed to predict the effect of intra-ply shearing; classical laminate theory and a modified rule of mixtures. The models are validated by

comparison with experimental results obtained from flat panels of sheared material. A finite element structural analysis is performed for the hemisphere which incorporates the effect of the fibre shearing. Comparisons are then made with the results of structural tests on the hemispheres.

DEFORMATION MODES OCCURRING DURING FORMING

Several two dimensional modes of deformation can occur during the forming of a single ply of composite material:

Fibre stretching

Fibre stretching is caused by tensile forces on the fibre tows, as shown in Fig. 1. Strains of more than 30% can occur during the forming process, however, as aerospace materials use high stiffness reinforcements (e.g. carbon) the fibre elongation can be neglected. The maximum fibre strain generally permitted for these types of materials is approximately 1% [1].

Fig. 1: Fibre stretching due to tensile forces.

Fibre straightening

This is again caused by tensile forces on the fibre tows and can result in strains of up to 10%. However, most fibre tows tend to be flat in practice which reduces the influence of the fibre straightening. As a result, this deformation mode may also be neglected.

Shear slip

Shear slip is produced by tensile forces acting perpendicular to the fibre direction, as shown in Fig. 2. However, as this mode only tends to occur at corners, it is not relevant to the hemisphere forming test used in this investigation.

Fig. 2: Shear slip of fibre tows.

Fibre shear

Shearing of the fibres is caused by tensile forces acting in a direction other than along the fibre tows, as shown in Fig. 3. This is the major deformation mode, causing strains of up to 30% [1]. To ensure accurate predictions of the formed components behaviour, the effect of this deformation mode must be considered during the analysis stage.

Fig. 3: Fibre shear due to tensile forces

Fibre buckling

Buckling of the fibre tows occurs as a result of compressive forces acting along the fibre direction. This can result in local wrinkles or larger global folds being formed which reduce the mechanical properties of the component. Consequently fibre buckling must be avoided during the forming process.

ANALYSIS METHODS

Classical laminate theory uses a unidirectional lamina as the basis on which to determine the stress-strain relationships for the composite laminate. At a constituent level the lamina is heterogeneous in nature, as the fibre properties differ from the matrix properties. However, classical theory adopts a macro-mechanical approach, requiring the stress and strain to be expressed as the averages of an equivalent homogenous material [2].

The modified rule of mixtures approach is derived from Krenchels work on fibre reinforced cements [3]. The material is considered to be a single lamina consisting of fibres at various orientations to the axis of loading. An efficiency factor (η) is generated for the laminate by examining the resulting strains in the fibres:

$$\eta = a_n \cos^4 \phi \quad (1)$$

Where a_n is the proportion of fibres at angle ϕ , and n is the total number of fibre groups. The efficiency factor is applied to the fibre terms of the rule of mixtures type equations to obtain the equivalent elastic modulus (E_x) and shear modulus (G_{xy}) for the laminate:

$$E_x = E_m (1-V_f) + E_f V_f \eta \quad (2)$$

$$G_{xy} = (1-V_f)G_m + E_f V_f a_n \sin^2 \phi \cos^2 \phi \quad (3)$$

This approach has the advantage of being able to allow for the changing fibre volume fraction resulting from the intra-ply shearing. This can be calculated from:

$$V_f = \frac{W N}{t \rho (\sin 2 \phi)} \quad (4)$$

Where W is the areal weight of the material (kg/m^2), N is the number of plies, t is the overall laminate thickness (m), and ρ is the fibre density (kg/m^3).

VALIDATION OF ANALYSIS METHODS

A series of 1.5 mm thick flat panels were produced to predetermined sheared fibre angles. The panels were manufactured from four plies of 5 Harness Satin weave Tenax HTA carbon fibre reinforcement with Hexcel Fibredux 6376 toughened epoxy resin. The laminates were deformed in a picture frame apparatus at 70°C with a strain rate of 1.0 mm/min. After curing, test coupons were cut from the panels as shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5: Arrangement of test coupons and sheared panels

The coupons were loaded along the axis of symmetry to obtain the equivalent elastic properties. A comparison of experimental results with predictions from the rule of mixtures and classical laminate models are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Comparison of predicted elastic modulus with experimental results

Fibre angle (degrees)	Classical laminate theory modulus value (GN/m ²)	Rule of mixtures modulus value (GN/m ²)	Experimental modulus (GN/m ²)
±35.6	33	28	29
±54.4	14	10	12

FORMING PROCESS DEVELOPMENT TRIALS

The trials were performed using 1.5 mm thick laminates of plain weave Torayca T300 carbon fibre reinforcement with Hexcel Fibredux 6376 toughened epoxy resin. The forming tool consisted of a 150 mm diameter male hemisphere form, over which the laminate was draped, together with a parallel section to allow for bridging of the test material, as shown in Fig 8. This shape has been widely used to analyse material drape [4, 5] as it represents a severe test of the materials ability to form. In addition, the varying rate of change of geometry over the hemisphere enables the material to be characterised by the distance over which it forms without wrinkling.

A single diaphragm vacuum forming process was employed in the trials, using a silicone rubber. The laminate plies were all orientated to 0° to align the areas of intra-ply shearing. This enabled the effects of the shearing to be seen more clearly. With this lay up, all intra-ply shearing occurred in the areas at 45° to the warp and weft fibres of the laminate.

Fig. 8: Hemisphere tool geometry.

Effect of vacuum rate

The time to reach atmospheric pressure was varied from thirty seconds to four minutes to establish the optimum vacuum rate for the forming process. The minimum of fibre wrinkling occurred when the time to reach atmospheric pressure was four minutes.

Test piece shape and size

The initial laminate shape was a square of 350 mm side length. Trials performed using this laminate resulted in similar patterns of fibre wrinkling; the largest wrinkles occurred in the warp and weft directions, with smaller wrinkles forming in the areas of intra-ply shear.

The warp and weft wrinkling resulted from compressive stresses induced by the intra-ply shearing at the corners of the test piece. This fibre buckling was prevented by using an octagonal flat laminate 400 mm across flats, which equalised the amount of material around the base of the forming tool. However, the wrinkling in the areas of shear increased, as shown in Fig 9, resulting in greater wrinkling of the hemisphere section.

Fig. 9: Top view of formed test piece showing wrinkling.

An octagonal flat laminate measuring 375 mm across flats was used to re-introduce some warp and weft wrinkling, thereby enabling the laminate to be formed without wrinkling over the hemisphere section.

Forming temperature

Initial trials performed between 60°C and 100°C produced similar results; the largest wrinkles occurred at the corners, together with smaller wrinkles at the sides of the test piece. The similarity in the wrinkling of the formed components was related to the small reduction in resin viscosity over this temperature range [6]. Increasing the forming temperature to 130°C reduced the resin viscosity to near its minimum value. The resulting wrinkling of the formed components was reduced by 17%.

Fig. 10: Photograph of formed test piece to show wrinkling.

Fig. 11: Photograph of formed test piece to show reduced wrinkling.

Having established the parameters of the forming process, a hemisphere component was produced from the 5 Harness Satin material used in the manufacture of the sheared panels.

TESTING AND ANALYSIS OF HEMISPHERE COMPONENTS

The hemisphere was loaded at diametrically opposite locations across its base, as shown in Fig. 12. Resulting deflections were measured at four orientations; 0° , 15° , 30° and 45° to the warp direction to demonstrate the stiffness variation due to intra-ply shearing.

At the 45° orientation a 200 kN load resulted in a deflection of 11 mm. This was 68.4% greater than the deflection observed at the 0° orientation under the same load, as shown in Fig. 13. At 0° orientation the fibres were still aligned in the direction of the applied load as

no intra-ply shearing had occurred. Whereas, at 45° the fibres were at maximum shear, hence the reduction in material stiffness.

Fig. 12: Diagram of pinch test performed on hemisphere components.

Fig. 13: Pinch test results for hemisphere component.

Two groups of finite element (FE) analysis models were produced; one using the modified rule of mixtures with the other using classical laminate theory. These groups were subdivided into models with constant and varying material properties. The varying property distribution was produced by dividing the model into eight zones, as shown in Fig. 14, based on the intra-ply shearing witnessed on the hemisphere. A different set of material properties was assigned to each zone. Predictions obtained from the models were compared with the relevant test results, as shown in Table 2.

Fig 14. Zoning of material properties for FE model.

Table 2. Comparison of FE model predictions to test results.

Orientation	Classical laminate theory - No zones			Rule of mixtures - No zones			Classical laminate theory - Zoned			Rule of mixtures - Zoned		
	Deflection			Deflection			Deflection			Deflection		
	FE	Test	Error	FE	Test	Error	FE	Test	Error	FE	Test	Error
0	3	4	-25	12	4	200	3	4	-25	4	4	0
15	-	-	-	-	-	-	3	5	-40	5	5	0
30	-	-	-	-	-	-	4	9	-56	6	9	-33
45	3	11	-73	3	11	-73	4	11	-64	6	11	-45

CONCLUSIONS

The hot drape forming experiments clearly demonstrated that the forming process was affected by a number of variables:

Geometry of laminate

The degree of fibre buckling depended on the area of material undergoing intra-ply shearing. Increasing this area relative to the surrounding material reduced the amount of wrinkling.

Vacuum rate

Although the application of the vacuum was restricted by the design of the forming equipment, it was apparent that the slower vacuum rates resulted in less wrinkling.

Forming temperature

To prevent the component curing during the forming process the temperature must be restricted to between 60°C and 100°C. Experiments have shown that the degree of wrinkling is consistent over this range. Increasing the temperature to the point of minimum resin

viscosity significantly reduces the degree of wrinkling. However, the forming process cannot be completed before the component begins to cure.

The sheared panel experiments demonstrated the accuracy of both the modified rule of mixtures and classical laminate models. Simulating the effect of fibre shearing in a finite element structural analysis improved the accuracy of the predicted deflections. The modified rule of mixtures model typically produced more accurate results due to the lower shear modulus values produced with this model. Examining the FE analysis showed the shear modulus to be the critical material property governing the behaviour of the component. This was further illustrated by the large error produced when the modified rule of mixtures model was used without allowing for intra-ply shearing.

The inaccuracies in the predicted deflection values are thought to be due to the size of the material zones in the finite element analysis. These zones are necessarily large as they are produced by manually modifying the element mesh used in the analysis. The predicted deflection values could be improved by increasing the number of material zones used. Ideally, the analysis would use a separate material property set for each element in the mesh, thereby allowing for the variation in intra-ply shearing occurring throughout the component.

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